

Determination Factors of Packaged Product Selling

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This examination means to research the job of bundling in customer's view of item quality at the packaged product. The study includes four free factors: Protection of items and buyer, Promotion of items, assistance of capacity, use, and accommodation of items, help of reusing and lessening ecological harm and the reliant variable is buyer's view of item quality at the Point of procurement. The analyst attempts to create and test a model to accomplish the exploration goals. Information was gathered from a comfort test of 547 respondents utilizing a poll. Survey comprises of 26 things estimated on five point likert scale. The information is investigated utilizing a few factual strategies to test the expressed speculations. Unmistakable factual measures are utilized to depict the examination's example qualities. Numerous relapse investigations are used to discover the impact of the free factors on the reliable variable. It was discovered that all the autonomous factors significantly affected Bangladeshi shopper's view of item quality at the purpose of procurement. Proposals for future research, promoting suggestions, and constraints of this examination are proposed.

Keywords: BUYER, PROCUREMENT, LIKERT SCALE, BANGLADESH, GOALS, PACKAGED PRODUCT, PROTECTION

Introduction

In business they say, “it’s the packaging that sells the product the first time, but it’s what’s inside that sells the package the second time.” How many

times have you seen a new product fail because the manufacturer has overlooked an aspect that prevented the product from moving off the shelf? It’s a costly mistake, especially when you consider the average food product launch ranges from \$12,000 to \$15,000. Launching your product to market can be fraught with difficulties.

To help you avoid this mistake we have provided below our “packaging recipe for success”, to help you launch your product cost efficiently and in a timely manner. Before starting this recipe however you will need to answer a few questions:

- What is your product’s market? How big is it? Is it a growth market or is it crammed with similar products?
- Who is going to purchase your product?
- What will make your product different from your competitors?

- What are your competitors doing well, and, just as importantly, what are they doing poorly?
- Is your product shelf stable, or are there special handling requirements that need to take into account?
- How are you going to produce your product? Are you going to manufacture it yourself or are you going to have a private label company manufacture it for you?
- If you are planning to manufacture it yourself, this opens a whole host of questions about machinery, location, processes, food safety, etc. If this is your route, do your homework in advance.

Bundling presently is viewed as a fundamental part of our cutting edge way of life and the manner in which business is sorted out. Bundling is the encasing of a physical article, commonly an item that will be offered available to be purchased. It is the procedure of getting ready things of gear for transportation and capacity and which grasps conservation, ID and bundling of items. Packaging is the demonstration of containing, securing and exhibiting the substance through the long chain of generation, dealing with and transportation to their goals in as great a state, as they were, at the hour of generation Packaging is a significant piece of the marketing process as it assumes a job in imparting the picture and personality of an organization. Because of expanding self-administration and changing buyers' way of life the enthusiasm for bundle as an instrument of offers advancement and trigger of imprudent purchasing conduct is developing progressively. So bundling has a significant job in advertising correspondences, particularly from the purpose of offers and could be treated as one of the most significant variables impacting Consumer's buy choice. Thusly the job of bundle in promoting correspondences builds: it must stand out for consumer and transmit satisfactory estimation of item to customer in the brief time frame directly in the spot of offer. In this manner there is a need to investigate bundle and its components in more detail, so as to comprehend which of these components are the most significant for shopper's buy choice. Specifically research says there are four significant capacities for bundling, and the present investigation centers around these capacities, to think about the job of bundling in buyer's impression of item quality at the purpose of procurement. These four measurements incorporate every one of kotlers' measurements however in different names, these measurements are: Protection of items and purchaser, Advancement of items, Facilitation of capacity, use, and comfort of items and Facilitation of reusing furthermore, lessening natural harm.

Materials and methods

The Problem Statement

When given the choice between two products, equal in price and function, targeted consumers buy the one they consider to be more attractive (Kotler and Rath 1984;).Packaging is gradually becoming a way to gain consumer's notice and attention, Today, virtually all goods that are manufactured or processed require some packaging in some phase of their production or distribution; Packaging decisions are to be considered in early marketing plans as an integral part of the total marketing strategy. Packaging is an important integrative aspect of the product and often a critical factor in the success or failure of a given product

The objectives of the Study

The importance of this study stems from the following reasons: 1- The scarcity of studies and scientific research dealing with the role of packaging in Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the point of purchase. According to the researcher's limited knowledge and after a comprehensive survey on the packaging literature in Bangladesh, this study is the first in packaging field especially for juice products. 2- It investigates the role of packaging in consumer's perception of product quality at the point of purchase. 3- The result of this study will be useful for companies that export their products to Bangladesh, companies that work in Bangladesh, and help Bangladeshi companies in designing their products' packages in a most appropriate way that helps to create a better awareness for their products. 4- The results of this study will be useful for academicians; 5- They can gain insights and suggestions for future research. 6. Research hypotheses In order to achieve the objectives designed for this study, the following research hypotheses are stated based on the revelation in the review of literature.

H01: There is no significant statistical effect of "the role of packaging in protecting the products and consumer" on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase **H02:** There is no significant statistical effect of "the role of packaging in promoting the products" on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase. **H03:** There is no significant statistical effect of "the role of packaging in facilitating the storage, use, and convenience of product" on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase. **H04:** There is no significant statistical effect of "the role of packaging in recycling and reducing environmental damage" on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase.

According to some researcher there are four important functions or roles for packaging. These roles are: Protection of products and consumer, Promotion of products, Facilitation of storage, use, and convenience of products and Facilitation of recycling and reducing environmental damage. This thesis attempts to study the role of packaging in Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the point of purchase. According to what mentioned above and based on the previous review of literature and related studies, the researcher suggests the following model.

Figure 1: Research model

Research Design

A deductive approach was designed for the purpose of this study, where data are collected using questionnaire. These data was used to test the research hypotheses and to answer the research questions and to identify the factors that have a significant effect on the consumer's perception of product quality at the point of purchase in the Bangladeshi context.

Population and Sample

Population can be defined as the entire group of people, event, or things that the researcher desire to investigate (Sekaran, 2004). Therefore, the population of this study consists of Bangladeshi consumers. A convenience sample of Bangladeshi consumers was selected from Bangladeshi consumers in three different locations distributed in DHAKA (The capital of Bangladesh) to generate a high level of representation to the study population. Total 600 questionnaires were distributed, 200 ones for each location. The total number of usable responses resulting from this process was 547(181 from Gulshan, 192 from East West University BD, 174 from Bashundhara) with a response rate up to 91%. This study was conducted on different types of juice as an example of consumer products.

Data Collection methods

Primary data were collected by using a questionnaire, while secondary data were obtained from previous researches and literature. The questionnaires were distributed directly to the participants selected as a study sample. The distribution and collection process took about four week's period. The questionnaire consisted of two major parts, the first part was designed to collect demographic data (gender, age, education level), and the second part contains 26 items distributed along five sections to measure the study variables. The questionnaire

was prepared in English; it is composed of 26 items measuring the independent variables and dependent variable of the study. The respondents indicated the frequency of encountering the situation described by each item using a five-point likert scale which ranges from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5).

Data analysis

As shown in table 2. 45.7% of respondents (250 respondents) were males, and 54.3% (297 respondents) were females, as it is obvious that the largest percentages of respondents were females. According to the age, the age category of "less than 20" are (26.3%) of the whole respondents, and the age category of "40 to 49" are (13%) of the whole respondents, the largest percentage was those respondents between "20 to 39" years old (56.5), and the lowest percentage was those respondents between "60 to more than" years old (4.2%).(21.6%) of the respondents are "high school to less than", (19.4%) are diploma degree, (8.4%) are MA degree, and (1.4%) are PhD degree, but the largest percent can be seen in Bachelor degree (49.2%).

Descriptive Statistics

In order to explore the existence and importance of every variable according to the sample of the study, means and standard deviations for the independent variables (protection, promotion, facilitation, and recycling) were calculated. The instrument of the study was scaled as follows:

Table (0): Views of the sample examined, according to the Likert scale and corresponding degrees.

Opinion	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Degrees	5	4	3	2	1

1 – 2.49	2.5 – 3.49	3.5 and above
Low	Medium	High

If the mean value of the statement is more than or equal to 3.5, then the level of agreement with the statement Measuring a certain variable is high, if the mean value ranges between (2.5 – 3.49), then the level of agreement is medium and when the mean value of the statement is equal to or less than (2.49), then the level of agreement with the statement is low. Table (3); represent the means and standard deviations for independent variables.

Hypotheses Testing

To test the hypothesis, it was deemed appropriate to use multiple regression estimations for testing the proposed hypotheses (Hair et al, 1998). To test multiple regression models, it is necessary to assess whether the collected data violate some key assumptions of regression models because any assumption violations can result in distorted and biased research results

These assumptions include co-linearity, linearity and normality. Multivariate normality is the assumption that all variables and all combinations of the variables are normally distributed.

When the assumption is met, the residuals are normally distributed and independent, the differences between predicated and obtained scores (errors) are symmetrically distributed around a mean of zero and there is no pattern to the errors. From the table (4), we can see that the variables are normally distributed, having skewers value between (-1 to 1). From the table we can see the all of these variables have skewers ranged from (-0.248) to (-0.752), which means that the variable are normal distribution. Multi-co-linearity can be controlled by two ways: tolerance values and values of variance inflation factor (VIF). Co-linearity high degrees could result in both regression coefficients being inaccurately estimated, and difficulties in separating the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Any variable with a tolerance value below (0.10) or with a value above (10.0) of (VIF) would have a correlation is more than 0.90 with other variables and indicative of the co-linearity problem. Result in table below (4-), shows that tolerance for all independent variables is more than (0.10) and VIP for independent variables is less than the limited valued (10.0), so the conclusion will be as there is no co-linearity between the independent variables of the model: the linear regression analysis of the original model reveals that the R-square of the model is (32.1%). This mean the model explains (32.1%) of the variance in the dependent variable (5). The model is statistically significant either, as the P-value for the model is (0.00). This means the fitness of model in explaining the customers' perception of product quality at the point of purchase is high. The following hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression analysis, to know if there is an impact of independent variable on the dependent variable. According to the decision rule: accept null hypothesis (H₀) if the significance level (α) of the variable is greater than (0.05) significance level, and reject (H₀) if the significance (α) in level of equal or less than (0.05) (Sekaran, 2004). According to the previous decision rule, the researcher has tested the proposed hypotheses and found the following results: Results showed that there is statistically significant impact for all independent variables (protection, promotion, facilitation, recycling) on the dependent variable (Bangladeshi Consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase). According to Beta values we can say that(facilitation of storage, use, and convenience of product) comes first on the most powerful variable in explaining the variance in dependent variable (perception of product quality), then it followed by protection of product, recycling and reducing environmental damage, and promotion of product.

Table (1) Cronbach's Alpha (α) for the Scales

Variables	A
Protection of products and consumer	0.715
Promotion of products	0.729
Facilitation of storage, use, and convenience of products	0.606
Facilitation of recycling and reducing environmental damage	0.635
Perception of products quality	0.758
Over all α coefficient	0.836

Table (2) Demographic Characteristics of the Respondent

<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Sex		
Male	250	45.7%
Female	297	54.3%
Level of education		
Higher school –less	224	41%
Diploma	269	49.2%
B.sc	46	8.4%
M.sc	8	1.4%
P.hd	00	00%
Age		
Less than 20	144	26.3%
20-39 years	309	56.5%
40-59 years	71	13%
60 and more	23	4.20%

Discussion of the Findings Based on table (6) the impact of the selected factors (Protection of products and consumer, Promotion of products, Facilitation of storage, use, and convenience of products, Facilitation of recycling and reducing environmental damage) on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the point of purchase can be concluded and the impact of these factors is discussed accordingly: It was found that there is a significant statistical effect of "The role of packaging in protecting the products and consumer" on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase. Studies show that protecting the products and consumer is a key and important role or function for the packaging. Increasing

attention is drawn to focus on package safety especially for drugs, household cleaners, and other products that are potentially dangerous, particularly to children. This finding is consisted with (Bix, 2002), who found that Packaging that fails to fully protect the product, has the potential to result in excess damage and waste, diminished shelf life, and loss of flavor or efficacy. Problems associated with insufficient protection are likely to lead to customer's dissatisfaction; this means there is a connection between the package's ability to protect the product and consumer's satisfaction or his perception of product quality. And also this finding is consisted with (Boyce et al, 2008), who found that the main features are considered desirable in take-out food (delivery food) packages these were: the ability to insulate food, to contain product without spillage, and to keep individual foods separate within the same package; this means that the ability of package to protect and contain the product is one of the desirable features by consumer in take-out food package which determine the consumer's willingness. This finding contradicts with (Tse, 1999), who found that the perceived product safety was significantly affected by: price, brand name, store name, promotion channels, source credibility, country of origin, nature of product testing authority and warranty. We can say that packaging is not mentioned as one of the factors that affect consumer perception for product safety; this indicates that there is no connection between product safety and consumer's perception. There is a significant statistical effect of "the role of packaging in promoting the products" on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase. This result is supported by (Pires, 2008), who found the Colors and shapes combinations which are consistent are expected to enhance consumers' product quality perception, and also this finding is supported by (EL-Omari, 1998), who found that there is a strong positive correlation between promotional role of packaging and consumers' attraction to good packaging. There is a significant statistical effect of "the role of packaging in facilitating the storage, use, and convenience of products" on Bangladeshi consumer's perception of product quality at the Point of purchase. This result is supported by (Ferrell, 1987), who found that the convenience is another function of packaging that consumers often look for at the point of purchase, the size or shape of a package may relate to the product's storage, convenience of use, or replacement rate, and by (Silayoi and Speece, 2004), who found that the Package size, shape effects customer judgments and decisions toward product quality, and also this finding is supported by (Lofgren, 2006), who found that the packaging design can Contribute in the display of quality through facilitating the storage, usage and consumption.

Table (3). Descriptive statistics for independent variables

Independent Variables	N	Mean	Standard deviations
Protection	547	3.86	.86
Promotion	547	3.92	.55
Facilitation	547	4.20	.54
Recycling	547	3.43	.86

Table (4). Fitness of the Model for Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig
1	0.566	0.321	0.316	0.47341	63.960	0.00

Table (5). Results of Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Un standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1(constant)	1.041	.196		5.314	0.00
Protection	.219	.041	.204	5.398	0.00
Promotion	.126	.026	.188	4.912	0.00
Facilitation	.270	.041	.262	6.583	0.00
Recycling	.131	.025	.198	5.207	0.00

Conclusion

A decent item bundle isn't junk; it's an incredible augmentation of your image.

Consistently observes the dispatch of just about 30,000 new items, and 70-80 percent of these items crash and burn. Here's the means by which and why you can beat the chances by focusing on your item bundling.

1. Makes you stick out

For each item available, there are endless brands competing for the client's consideration. One approach to clear the messiness and stand apart from the group is to guarantee that your item bundling is charming. You can go fantastically striking and lively to stand out, use stylization with particular examples to make your bundling sparkle, or recount to a remarkable story with your bundling. You have unlimited conceivable outcomes to make your item bundling represent itself with no issue.

2. Impacts customers buy aim

The human mind responds to examples and hues in extraordinary manners, so pick your hues admirably. Concentrate your statistic and in like manner alter item bundling for greatest effect at the retail rack.

3. Makes an extraordinary promoting instrument

Individuals settle on their buy choice close to being given the item. This is the reason the item bundling makes a splendid advertising apparatus. Messages can carry a grin to your face or trigger a sweet memory. Informing has enthusiastic intrigue, which has demonstrated fruitful for brands. So it just bodes well that your

item bundling can incorporate messages like "new look, same enrapturing aroma" or "now get 30% extra in each bundle."

4. Builds brand acknowledgment

Ever asked why shoppers perceive marked items in a moment? Item bundling that incorporates the organization logo with the correct text styles and hues lifts brand acknowledgment as well as expands psychological review. So, pause for a minute to make those minor changes to leave a gigantic effect on the shopper's psyche.

Item bundling has the ability to take your deals from droop to knock if it's intended to make that wow factor. Here are four different ways to utilize your bundling configuration to make more deals.

1. Realize your objective market to have an effect.

For a splendid bundling configuration, consistently think about the statistic foundation first. It is critical to know the individuals who need what you have in the event that you need to be fruitful in a focused market. Comprehend your intended interest group, their torment focuses, their inclinations and their purchasing propensities, and alter your bundling as needs be.

2. Make minimal effort bundling look chic with customization.

Extraordinary bundling doesn't really mean costly bundling. A few brands have had an effect even with straightforward item bundling. You can step up your bundling methodology basically by including layers, surfaces or polished typography. Truth is told, a basic bundling configuration demonstrates to be progressively viable if the market is outwardly disturbed.

3. Utilize astute bundling to make an unpacking knowledge.

Nothing works superior to activating enthusiastic commitment, so in the event that you can get your item bundling to make the customer feel something, it's certain to make a buzz in the market. Similarly, as individuals love to unpack an Apple item, if your bundling can offer a fun, hands-on involvement, it makes certain to hop off the rack and into the shopping basket.

4. Go eco-accommodating with the plan to support your image character.

Any item bundling that can be reused or reused makes certain to speak to the eco-cognizant buyer of today. Truth is told; in excess of 50 percent of individuals pick an eco- accommodating brand over others. In the event that your item bundling has a positive ecological effect, you can make extraordinary walks in the market.

Your customers are effectively screening different items at the same time. The surest method to have any kind of effect now of thought is going shrewd with your item bundling.

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